

PROBLEM- BASED TECHNIQUE IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Abstract.

Problem based learning is a pedagogical technique that places learning in complex problem solving contexts. This gives students the opportunity to think about how their findings relate to a particular problem. It makes them wonder what they need to know. The article discusses the main points of problem- based techniques in a foreign language teaching.

Keywords.

problem-based learning, self-education, individual and group work, flexibility, creative thinking.

Introduction.

Problem-based learning is the modern level of development of didactics and advanced pedagogical practice. It arose as a result of the achievements of advanced practice and theory of education and upbringing and, in combination with the traditional type of education. The name itself is connected not so much with the etymology of the word as with the essence of the concept.

Learning is not called problematic because students learn all the educational material only by independently solving problems and “discovering” new concepts. Here there is an explanation of the teacher, and the reproductive activity of students, and the setting of tasks, and the implementation of exercises by students²³³. However, the organization of the educational process is based on the principle of problems, and the systematic solution of educational problems is a characteristic feature of this type of education. Since the whole system of methods is aimed at the comprehensive development of the student, the development of his

²³³ Махмутов М. И. Организация проблемного обучения в школе. Книга для учителей. М. : Просвещение, 1977. 240 с. Махмутов М. И. Ленинская теория отражения и дидактика // М. И. Махмутов. Советская педагогика. 1980. № 4. С. 59-64.

cognitive needs, the formation of an intellectually active personality, problem-based learning is a truly developmental learning.

Literature review:

In the pedagogical literature, there are a number of attempts to define this phenomenon. By problem-based learning, V. Okon understands “a set of such actions as organizing problem situations, formulating problems (students themselves gradually get used to this), providing students with the necessary assistance in solving problems, checking these solutions, and, finally, managing the process of systematizing and consolidating acquired knowledge » [36,208]. It seems to us that the formulation of V. Okon concerns the essence of the process of problem-based teaching, i.e., the activity of a teacher, and does not express the goal of organizing problem-based learning. The activity of the student is only implied here. The main drawback of this definition is that the learning process appears here as a process of acquiring all knowledge only by solving problems. Such a principle of organizing learning is methodologically unacceptable from the point of view of the theory of problem-based learning. Among Soviet teachers there is a different approach to the definition of this concept. For example, D.V. Vilkeev, by problem-based learning, means such a nature of learning when it is given some essential features of scientific knowledge (D.V. Vilkeev, 1967). This definition has the disadvantage that, firstly, the features of scientific knowledge are attached to the entire learning process, which is impossible in principle: the teaching process cannot have such features; secondly, the definition does not reveal the essence of the type of learning, but only points to one of its features.

Analysis:

Problem-based learning is a link that ensures the creative participation of students in the process of acquiring new knowledge, the formation of students' ability to act flexibly and adapt to constantly changing life situations, the ability to acquire independently the missing knowledge, is a set of methods and means for self-knowledge. The goals of problem-based learning in foreign language classes are to develop students' ability to flexibly navigate, adapt to constantly changing life situations, independently acquire the In problem-based teaching of foreign languages, two forms of work with students predominate: individual and group, as there are objective psychological reasons for this. There are students who like to work alone, regardless of their level of training, but there are also those who want to be guided or constantly helped. Some love and may think that others cannot or do not want to, but are willing to do whatever they are told. Combining students into groups according to different levels of abilities contributes in the process of

joint work to the self-education of each, the development of a sense of mutual assistance and responsibility for the overall result. However, there are also disadvantages, namely: individual students in the group do not quite conscientiously perform the assigned tasks, thereby reducing the assessment of joint work, which sometimes causes friction, mutual accusations, etc.

The method of problem-based learning differs from the traditional one in that it puts the student in a position where he is forced to think actively and intensively, mobilizing his intellectual potential to solve the problem and form a theoretical conclusion. The specifics of the creation and the peculiarities of posing problem situations in teaching a foreign language are related to the following issues: the formation and development of the skills of students and teachers to work with problem situations; professional needs and capabilities of teachers in managing the process of resolving problem situations; features of creating problem situations on the basis of problem-communicative tasks; cognitive and communicative needs and opportunities of trainees in "appropriation" of problem situations [2,174]. Based on the definition of a problem situation that arises when there is a problem, an obstacle on the way to achieving the goal, the goal complicated by the obstacle should become a known component of the problem situation. Components such as place, time, participants in communication may be optional, unknown, while the number of unknown components determines the degree of complexity of the situation, as well as the variability of solutions. In addition, it is necessary to determine the maximum value of the unknown components, at which the problem situation, as too complex, cannot be set by the trainees, as well as the minimum value at which the problem situation, as too easy, ceases to be a problem, turning into problem-free situations. Often, when teaching a foreign language, "step-by-step" problem situations are used, in which the goal is complicated not by one, but by a number of sequentially proposed obstacles. To ensure optimal conditions for students to set problem situations (according to I. A. Zimnyaya), these situations must meet certain requirements that are correlated with the cognitive and communicative needs and capabilities of a particular contingent of students²³⁴.

As part of teaching a foreign language, under the cognitive and communicative needs of students, one can understand the interest in resolving problem situations in their native and foreign languages, and under the cognitive and communicative capabilities - the ability to resolve such situations in their own

²³⁴ Khalilova OA. Organizational Aspects of Developing Innovative Methods in Teaching. Eastern European Scientific Journal. 2018 Apr 10(2). <http://journale.auris-verlag.de/index.php/EESJ/article/viewFile/891/965>.

language. Since problem situations are presented in the form of problem tasks, let us consider these tasks. Cognitive-linguistic tasks should be based on interesting forms of presentation (visibility, charades, crossword puzzles, riddles), cognitive-communicative tasks can be created on the basis of modeling easily accessible life situations, spiritual and cognitive tasks should be based on solving the problems of the inner world. Accordingly, problem situations and problem tasks must meet the requirements consistent with the cognitive and communicative needs and abilities of students.

Linguistic foreign language abilities include - the use of a more complex structure of the statement (the number of individual turns, the use of phrases of greater length, complex and compound sentences); for speech - a more formalized mechanism for selecting words (less repetitions of a lexical and syntactic nature, pauses of hesitation); semantic - a wider coverage of the subject of discussion (the number of denotations and their subject features, the depth of understanding of the speech message).

Conclusion: Thus, we can conclude that problem-based learning is used both at the stage of introducing educational material and at the stage of its consolidation in the process of speech practice at different stages of education, both in traditional and non-standard lessons. Moreover, the conditions for setting learning situations by students are largely determined by the correspondence of these situations to their needs and the ability to resolve these situations in their native and foreign languages. Problem-based learning in a foreign language lesson helps to find the most effective ways and means of transforming reproductive thinking into effective, creative thinking.

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